

THE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS MORBIDITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Acute intestinal infections (AII) remain a global problem and are the leading cause of prevalence and high mortality. According to the World Health Organization, more than 4 billion cases of acute intestinal infections are reported worldwide every year. Every year, up to 180 million cases of viral diarrhoea are reported worldwide, the main cause being rotavirus and norovirus. Etiological decipherment and differential diagnosis of viral and bacterial diarrhoea remain low, leading to the irrational use of antibiotics.

Keywords: diarrhea, acute intestinal infections, viruses, bacteria, microbiosis.

Relevance. Acute intestinal infections (AII) remain a global problem to date, with a leading prevalence and high mortality rate, especially among children aged 0-3 years [1]. According to WHO, more than 4 billion cases of AII are reported worldwide every year, 60.0% of which occur in early childhood (0-3 years) [4]. Among the causes of AII, early childhood children are mainly affected by viral and viral bacterial diarrhoea, which can cause intra-hospital outbreaks and often runs in a severe form. Worldwide, up to 180 million cases of viral diarrhoea are reported annually, the main cause being the Rotoviruc and Norovirus [3]. Enteropatogenic and enterotoxigenic ectopic are important in the etiology of bacterial secretory diaries. Etiological decipherment and differential diagnosis of viral and bacterial diarrhoea remains low, leading to the irrational use of antibiotics [2].

Results: For 3 months of 2024, a total of 1979 cases of acute intestinal infections (AII) were registered, the intensity was 65.1 per 100,000 population. In the same period of 2023, 2,804 patients were registered, the intensive rate was 94.8. This year, the morbidity decreased by 29.4%.

Figure 1. Incidence of acute intestinal infections (AII) in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the period under study

Among the intestinal infections, acute intestinal infections of unclear etiology accounted for 96.6% (1910 cases), acute intestinal diseases were detected in the etiology - 2.4% (48 cases), bacterial dysentery - 1.0% (20 cases).

Figure 2.

Acute intestinal diseases were revealed in 48 cases (45 cases - rotavirus and 3 patients - E.coli) whose pathogens were identified, which is 23.8% lower than that of last year. The number of outstanding OQI decreased by 29.6% compared to last year.

Registered 1557 cases among children under 14 (78.7%), of which 562 cases - children under 1 (36.1%), 612 cases - children between 1 and 3 years (39.3%), 4,277 people aged 6-7 years (17.8%), 106 people aged 7-14 years (6.8%), also 47 people aged 15-19 years (2.4%), 375 (18.9%) - 20 years and over.

1412 people (71.4%) from OKI are unorganized children, 39 (2.0%) of them organized children, 136 (6.9%) - schoolchildren, 392 - adults (19.8%), of which 21 (5.4%) - students. No employees of catering establishments and similar groups were identified.

In the analysis of the factors of disease transmission in AII patients, it was suspected that the disease was caused by food in 96.7% of cases, of which 81.8% mainly due to consumption of various types of food, 7.8% - fruits and vegetables, 10.1% - through dairy products, 0.3% - through soft drinks, 2.1% - unspecified factors of transmission of diseases, 1.2% of cases - contact-domestic way.

Bacterial dysentery was reported in 20 patients and bacteriologically confirmed in 11 patients. Sh. Flexneri - 6 (54.5%) Sh. sonnei - 3 (27.3%), other shigellae - 2 (18.2%).

Among children under 14 years of age, 16 cases of bacterial dysentery (80.0%) were recorded, of which 2 cases (12.5%) - among children under 1 year, 8 cases (50.0%) - among

children 1-3 years old, persons aged 4-6 years were 6 children - 37.5%, persons aged 7-14 years were not registered, 4 (20.0%) patients were among 20- and-over age group.

Figure 3. Analysis of the factors of transmission of acute intestinal infections (AII)

Bacterial dysentery patients 15 (75.0%) were unorganized children, 1 (5.0%) was organized child, students were not registered, 4 of them were adults (20.0%).

Salmonella disease was registered in 40 patients for 3 months 2024, the intensity rate was 1.3, compared to the same period of 2023. The morbidity decreased by 31.0%. All patients had bacteriologically confirmed disease: of this, *Sal. typhi murium* was detected in 1 person (2.5%), *Sal. enteritidis* in 25 (62.5%), other salmonella - in 14 patients (35.0%).

Out of the total number of patients, 21 were adults (52.5%), 19 were children under 14 years (47.5%).

The main factors of transmission were eggs and poultry - 30.0%, meat products - 7.5%, fish and fish products - 2.5%, home cooking products - 20.0%, fruits and vegetables - 5.0%, milk and dairy products - 27.5%, salads - 5.0%, other foods - 2.5%.

In further studies we analyzed retrospectively medical records of sick children who were on hospital treatment at the clinic of the Research Institute of Epidemiology, Microbiology, infectious diseases in the department of intestinal diseases to assess the clinical course of rotavirus infection in children. The clinical study included 55 patients under 5 years of age with a verified etiological diagnosis of "rotavirus infection". All patients were tested with conventional clinical and laboratory methods. The rotavirus infection diagnosis was confirmed by detection of relevant serological markers by immunophenomenic analysis and polymerase chain reaction [5].

As a result, in the etiological structure of acute diarrhoea among declassified infections, the share of rotavirus infection was 27% in the period under study. In most cases the disease was of type gastroenteritis (71%) and in medium form (75%). Children under 1 year of age were 17 (31%), 1-3 years - 30 (54%), 3-5 years - 8 patients (15%). The disease was severe and the whole symptom complex developed in the first three days of the disease. In 87% of the patients, there was an increase in body temperature to febrile values, vomiting and diarrhea were observed in all

children. The intoxication syndrome was characterized by weakness, decreased appetite, paleness of the skin of patients. Cataract phenomena in the form of hypothermia and moderate manifestation of rhinitis were more frequently observed in children under 1 year ($p < 0.05$). Thus, a liquid, watery green or brown color stool is registered in 15% of the patients, a sputum-like stool and without pathogenic impurities up to 10 times a day - in 52% and more than 10 times - in 33% of the patients. Abdominal pain syndrome in the form of stomach pains was often reported in children over 3 years. Abdominal pain was not clearly localized and always accompanied by rumbling along the bowel. The duration of the main clinical symptoms varied between age groups. Duration of fever, vomiting, meteorism were reliably higher in children under 1 year ($p < 0.05$). Duration of diarrhea was reliably longer in children under 1 year - 5.02 days, in children 1-3 years - 4.203 days, 3-5 years - 3.103 days.

Conclusions: rotavirus infection was 27% among confirmed acute diarrhoeal diseases. Rotavirus infection in children was characterized by acute onset and moderate forms of the disease were prevalent. More pronounced manifestation and prolonged clinical symptoms were observed in children under 1 year. The current course of rotavirus infection is manifested by characteristic clinical changes that can serve as criteria for diagnosis of the disease.

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